

Space Time Slices in Quantum and Classical Mechanics

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In classical physics, velocity follows from exact measurements of space and time intervals (i.e perfect resolution of both). Inertial mass follows from a resistance of an object to a force (push or pull). Momentum, however, which nonrelativistically is mv and should be associated with ideas of inertial mass, and space time resolution may be instead linked to the physical idea of an impulse. An impulse seems to be like a hit and does not appear to be linked directly to space time physically, although its consequences are i.e. a particle receiving the impulse moves in space and time. In classical mechanics, $x(t)$ and so one considers either equally spaced dt intervals and corresponding $dx(t)$ or vice versa (constant dx) if an integral only involves space dependent values.

In quantum mechanics, one has two uncertainty principles, one related to E and t and the other to p and x . We argue that p is linked to the notion of an impulse which does not on the surface involve space or time. Given that p , even in nonrelativistic quantum mechanics, is mv there should at least be some built in notion of dx and dt . From the uncertainty principles one sees that dx (i.e. the wavelength) is linked to \hbar/p and dt to \hbar/E . Thus neither dt nor dx are constants, but depend on the motion. In the high energy quantum limit $dt \rightarrow W(x)W(x) dx \rightarrow 1/v(x) dx$ where $v(x)$ is classical velocity and $W(x)$ the bound state wavefunction. The bound state wavefunction, however, applies to the envelope of WW (not the actual crests and troughs) and so the dx - dt scheme which emerges is a smoothed over one and not the actual dx - dp of quantum mechanics. We try to examine some of these ideas in this note.

Classical Mechanics

We try to first consider some ideas of classical mechanics in a hand-wavy manner. Imagine a box filled with sand on a very smooth surface with no friction or air resistance. At first one might think that an infinitesimal force is needed to move the box because there is no apparent resistance. The box, however, may move with different velocities which implies different pushes or pulls (i.e. forces). This already suggests that inertial "mass" resists force. Alternatively, one may consider a force F_0 , which when applied to the box makes it move with velocity v_0 . If there are two identical boxes, $2F_0$ is needed so force is linked to inertial mass. Applying an impulse is not only linked to inertial mass, but to space-time because the box starts to move. Thus the idea of a physical impulse is somehow linked to space time resolution.

If instead of filling the stationary box with sand, one fills it with objects moving back and forth it seems that force is needed to make these move faster or slow them down if the box is moving. Thus an object moving back and forth within a stationary box is like a mass. A relationship is needed to directly link it to inertial mass. (This turns out to be $E=mc^2$.) Furthermore if there is "mass" associated with the moving object within the box, an object moving in one direction should have an enhancement of its inertial mass due to the motion. (Again a specific relationship is needed i.e. $m = m_0/\sqrt{1-v^2/c^2}$.)

In classical mechanics, one thinks of fixed dimensions in space as there is perfect resolution of space time. If one uses $x(t)$ then dt may be considered to be a constant and one has $dx(t)$. One, however, often has integrals consisting solely of space dependent functions. In such a case it is easier to use constant dx slices. If one considers the classical Action = $\int dt L$, then dt represents constant slices. One may switch to constant dx slices by using $dx/v(x) = dt$ i.e. using the determinant of a Jacobian.

Quantum Mechanics

We have argued in previous notes that quantum mechanics is based on the idea of impulse i.e. momentum. This does not seem to be implicitly linked to space time, yet nonrelativistic momentum retains its classical mechanical definition of mv . In previous notes we tried to link to spatial resolution by arguing that spatially invariant probability functions associated with impulse must recreate $V(x)$ i.e. we used $\exp(ipx)$ so that $\exp(ip_1 x)\exp(ip_2 x)$ equals $\exp(ip_1 + p_2)x$. In this note we argue that p which is linked to the physical notion of impulse, must somehow also carry with it the idea of space time slices in order that v (velocity) be defined. We argue that the uncertainty principles linked to the idea of a frequency in time and wavelength in space allow for this. Unlike classical physics, however, neither dt nor dx is considered to be a constant. Rather they are linked to energy and momentum i.e. $dx = \hbar/p$ and $dt = \hbar/E$. This yields a velocity which is $2v$ and not v , but we think that the basic idea of velocity v is present. (In some representations of the uncertainty principle $0.5\hbar$ is used and in other \hbar .) Thus space-time slices are directly associated with p which itself has the physical sense of an impulse. In particular, one may measure momentum by its effects upon hitting an object and not by measuring velocity (i.e. having space and time resolution) and inertial mass. (For example a ball with a certain velocity may break a piece of glass.) In previous notes, we have argued that quantum mechanics is based on impulse hits which may occur at any position. In order to link these with dt and dx , space-time becomes directly linked to energy and momentum which is something that does not happen in classical mechanics. In other words, there is no predetermined space-time in quantum mechanics (unless one has constant p). In a bound state, p is continually changing due to stochastic hits from $\exp(ipx)$ terms in $V(x)$ and so dt - dx slice values are also continually changing.

Classical Action

In previous notes, we argued that one may obtain quantum mechanics for a free particle by writing constant $v = x/t$ and varying the action with respect to x and t independently. After this variation x/t is again set to v . One does not vary x and t independently subject to a constraint i.e. $x/t = v$. The notion of $dx \rightarrow \hbar/p$ and $dt \rightarrow \hbar/E$ follow from this result as one finds that $dAction/dt = -E$ and $dAction/dx = p$ so that $\exp(-iEt + ipx)$ behaves in a similar manner and is a solution of the Schrodinger equation. Thus the idea of a time and space resolution also follows from the classical action.

High Energy Quantum Limit

Classical mechanics is based on either a constant dt or constant dx . Quantum mechanics, on the other hand, depends on $dx \rightarrow 1/p$ and $dt \rightarrow 1/E$. It may be noted, however, that in quantum mechanical bound states for any energy, there is a $v_{rms}(x)$ which is entirely classical. Thus, one may apply either a constant dx or dt to $v_{rms}(x)$ even though dx, dt associated with each p differs and is energy-momentum dependent. For high energy, it seems that particular p values dominate at each x and approximate $v_{rms}(x)$. This only occurs in an average sort of way because $W(x)W(x)dx$ where $W(x)$ is the wavefunction with crests and troughs only matches $1/v(x) dx$ ($v(x)$ =classical velocity) if one uses only the envelope. $W(x)W(x)$, however, is not really just an envelope. By considering only the envelope, one ignores quantum features i.e. the idea that dx, dt slices are still linked to $1/p$ and $1/E$. Thus, one "smoothes over" and obtains the classical picture in which space and time are defined everywhere with one slice (either dx or dt being considered constant).

Consequences

As a result, one must be careful when comparing quantum mechanics to theories based on a space time framework which already exists in all of space. This is the approach of classical mechanics etc. In quantum mechanics, dx and dt represent resolution and are directly linked to E and p . In the case of E for a bound state, different $\exp(ip_1x)$ terms from the particle combine with $\exp(ikx)$ terms from $V(x)$ to create $\exp(ipx)$. This involves an interval of time and so $1/E$ is linked to this time and shows why it is not perfectly sharp. The higher the energy, the sharper the time interval $1/E$.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we argue that in classical mechanics space and time are predetermined and one may consider either dt or dx to be constant. For example, if one has $x(t)$, one may choose to have dt constant. If one has an integral over dx and uses functions of x , then it is convenient to have dx constant. For example, $dt \rightarrow dx / v(x)$ where $v(x)$ is velocity. The idea of impulse (which is linked to p momentum) already exists in classical physics. Nonrelativistic p , however, is mv and so is automatically linked to dx and dt . We argue that quantum mechanics is based on impulses which are directly linked to p which is still defined as mv . Thus there should be some sense of dx and dt , yet we argue there is no fixed space time notion. Rather, dx and dt are linked to p and E i.e. $dx \rightarrow 1/p$ and $dt \rightarrow 1/E$ in other words resolutions. Each p in a bound state represents different dx, dt slices and in no situation is either constant (except for a fixed p free particle with no $V(x)$). In the high energy limit, $W(x)W(x)$ approximates $1/v(x)$ if one considers only the envelope of $W(x)W(x)$. In such a case, one smoothes out quantum mechanics and creates the space-time picture of classical physics.